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21.-24. svibnja 2015. / May 21-24, 2015
Kongresni centar Cap Aureo / Congress Centre Cap Aureo

5.

HRVATSKI KONGRES FARMACIJE
S MEĐUNARODNIM SUDJELOVANJEM

CROATIAN CONGRESS ON PHARMACY
WITH INTERNATIONAL PARTICIPATION

Farmaceutska izvrsnost u službi zdravlja
Pharmaceutical Excellence Dedicated to Health

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Knjiga sažetaka
Book of Abstracts

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 i / and
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5. hrvatski kongres farmacije
 s međunarodnim sudjelovanjem
5th Croatian Congress on Pharmacy
 with International Participation

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PREDGOVOR

Knjiga sažetaka obuhvaća sažetke pristigle do 10. ožujka 2015. Znanstvena i stručna predavanja Kongresa obuhvaćena su navedenim tematskim cjelinama:

- Bioetika u farmaciji
- Bolničko ljekarništvo
- Farmaceutska izobrazba i trajno usavršavanje
- Farmaceutski menadžment i marketing
- Farmaceutske znanosti
- Fitofarmacija i dodaci prehrani
- Javno ljekarništvo
- Javnozdravstveni projekti
- Klinička farmacija
- Kozmetologija i dermatofarmacija
- Regulatorna lijekova
- Tradicija i inovacije u izradi magistralnih i galenskih pripravaka
- Zdravstvena ekologija
- Različito

Sažetci su navedeni ovim redoslijedom: plenarna predavanja, predavanja, radionice, poster i promotivna predavanja.

Sažetci predavanja i izlaganja na posterima razvrstani su po tematskim cjelinama. Sažetci promotivnih predavanja navedeni su redoslijedom izlaganja.

U Knjigu sažetaka uvrštena je nova verzija Međunarodne farmaceutske prisege (FIP, 2014).

PREFACE

Book of Abstracts comprises abstracts received until 10 March, 2015. Scientific and professional Congress papers refer to the following thematic sections:

- Bioethics in pharmacy
- Hospital pharmacy
- Pharmaceutical education and training
- Pharmaceutical management and marketing
- Pharmaceutical sciences
- Phytopharmacy and food supplements
- Community pharmacy
- Public health projects
- Clinical pharmacy
- Cosmetology and dermatopharmacy
- Regulation of medicines
- Tradition and innovations in pharmaceutical compounding
- Health ecology
- Miscellaneous

Abstracts are given in the following order: plenary lectures, lectures, workshops, poster and promotional presentations.

Abstracts of oral and poster presentations are assorted according to thematic sections. Abstracts of promotional presentations follow the order of presentation.

In the Book of Abstracts the new version of the International Oath of a Pharmacist (FIP, 2014) was included.

P/KF-101
**EXPOSURE TO CLINICALLY SIGNIFICANT DRUG-ANTIHYPERTENSIVE AGENT INTERACTIONS IN PRIMARY HEALTH CARE
IZLOŽENOST INTERAKCIJAMA LIJEK-ANITIHIPERTENZIVNI AGENS U PRIMARNOJ ZDRAVSTVENOJ ZAŠTITI**
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Introduction: Drug-drug interactions are well-known-risk factor for adverse drug events (ADEs) which are often preventable.

Purpose: To identify the frequency and type of potential drug-antihypertensive agent interactions among outpatients in the Health Centre Novi Sad (HCNS), and to define recommendations for their management.

Method: Cross sectional prescription database study was conducted. The analysis randomly included 3452 outpatients with polypharmacy (prescribing ≥ 2 drugs and where at least one drug was antihypertensive agent for systematic use) who visited HCNS over 1-month period (November 1-30, 2011). All drug-drug combinations involving antihypertensives were identified according to *Drug Interaction Facts*. Additionally, based on the compendium, potential interactions (pls) were classified into categories *pharmacological mechanisms, clinical risk and management advice*.

Results: Overall 1210 clinically significant pls involving antihypertensives were identified among 926 (20,7 %) exposed patients (the mean age 67.5 ± 11.1 years; the mean number of prescribed drugs 6.1 ± 2.2 ; the mean number prescribed of antihypertensive agents 2.7 ± 0.94 , 61.3 % females). Risk for exposure was increased by patient age, number of prescribed drugs as well as number of prescribed antihypertensive agents (OR = 1.02, 95 % CI 1.01-1.02, $p < 0.001$; OR = 1.61, 95 % CI 1.54-1.69, $p < 0.001$; OR = 1.22, 95 % CI 1.12-1.34, $p < 0.001$, consequently). The proportion of pls was 20.8 % for angiotensin-converting-enzyme inhibitors, 35.5 % for β -adrenergic antagonist, 24.3 % for potassium sparing diuretics, 23.1 % for thiazide diuretics, 18.3 % for calcium channel antagonists, 7.8 % for loop diuretics, 1.4 % for angiotensin II receptor antagonist, and 0.5 % for α -adrenergic antagonists. Pharmacological mechanisms were classified as pharmacodynamic (65.1 %), pharmacokinetic (28.2 %), a combination of both types (14.5 %) and unknown (1.0 %). Potential clinical outcomes were increased risk for ADEs (primarily arrhythmias, electrolyte disbalance) and risk for decreased drug effectiveness (primarily sulfonylureas, antihypertensives) in 77.8 % and 30.7 % of cases, consequently. Management advice, besides monitoring of concurrent use of drugs (primarily monitoring of physiological markers, 72.2 % of cases), were considered as avoid coadministration (11.2 %), risk-modifying strategy (23.4 %), adjust dose as needed (60.2 %) and contraindication for simultaneous administration (0.6 %).

Conclusion: Every fifth outpatient with polypharmacy involving antihypertensive prescriptions was exposed to risk for clinically significant drug-antihypertensive interaction. Information based on the results of present study could be integrated in existing computerized physician order entry system in the HCNS as a form of clinical decision support.